

INFLUENCE OF PRIVATE TUTORING ON THE SSC LEVEL LEARNERS: A CASE STUDY OF GAZIPUR DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

Private Tutoring in English Language Learning is a common picture among the SSC level students. Many learners are very eager to receive private tutoring supports in ELT. Parents rely on private tutoring so that their children can cut a good figure in the examination. Monthly payment in private tutoring is on the increase day by day in Bangladesh. For this purpose, this study aims to look at the important reasons of private tutoring in English Language Learning in the SSC level of 21st century Bangladesh Education System. It would like to analyze the problems of the students why they are weak in English language. To carry out this research project under the Gazipur District near the capital city Dhaka of Bangladesh, 10 schoolteachers, 5 tutors, 25 students of SSC level, and 15 parents were selected for interview with a questionnaire pattern. An observation was done in the classroom to investigate the performance of the teachers and tutors while teaching English. The findings from the survey show that most of the SSC level students receive private tutoring support; and they have a keen attitude towards English Language Learning provided by private tutors rather than schoolteachers. Private tuition has both positive and negative aspects. Parents as well as learners should understand the importance of private tutoring and at the same time they ought to be conscious of problematic aspects of private tutoring as well.

Keywords: Private Tutoring, Tutors, SSC Level Students, Parents, and Teachers.

Introduction

Private Tutoring in academic subjects is defined as tutoring provided on a supplementary basis at the end of the school day, at weekends, or during vacations. It is paid for by fees and it typically involves two individuals, a tutor (the teacher or the person who helps someone to learn any subjects) and a tutee (the person being taught). The tutor is more knowledgeable or expert than the tutee, and attempts to help the tutee learn, usually in an academic area. Age is not necessarily a factor in the tutoring relationship – the tutor and tutee may be the same age – as long as the tutor

has greater knowledge or skill than the tutee. Traditionally, tutoring has involved one-to-one instruction, but some tutoring programs do involve a tutor and two or three tutees. Tutoring does not include extracurricular subjects, such as sports and art lessons, or family members on voluntary basis. (Bray, 2003, p.13)

Private Tutoring is a widespread phenomenon in many developing and developed countries around the globe. It is a byproduct and a feature of certain educational system which makes to establish a place for its prevailing system. This is the case in the educational system among the secondary level students in Bangladesh where private tutoring is on the increase across the country despite the government has taken some protesting steps against it. Private tutoring does affect many subjects, like English, Mathematics, Accounting, and Science in the Bengali Educational Curriculum; though certain subjects take the lion's share of attention of the SSC learners. One of these subjects is English as a foreign language (EFL). This is due, for the major part, to the importance of this language in future studies or job opportunities in Bangladesh.

In Bangladesh, many SSC level learners have a strong motive towards private tutoring; they think that there is no alternative means without private tutoring. Guidance have also same motive like their children. Both parents and students think that private tutoring can bring for them a brilliant success in each examination.

The current study wants to examine the issues of private tutoring in relation to the subject of English Language Learning, with a consideration of its reasons and impacts on Bangladeshi students' learning motivation. To acquire the target, the study has taken interviews of 25 students as well as their parents to investigate the real picture what makes them adhere to private tutoring and what impacts it has on their learning. The reasons as stated above, the researcher did carry out the mini research project in the English Language Home (known as Coaching Centre) situated at a local area, Tongi under the Gazipur district of Bangladesh with a view to investigating a new dimension of 21st -century ELT in the SSC level of Bangladesh Education System.

Literature Review

Private Tutoring is defined as fee-based tutoring that provides supplementary instruction to children in academic subjects they study in the mainstream education system. (Dang & Rogers, 2008, p.161) Bangladesh is a developing country and private tutoring in Bangladesh is delivered by mainstream teachers, teachers from other institutions or even non-teachers. Lessons occur one-to-one, in small groups (5-10 students) or in large groups (20 students or more). The venue of the teaching can be tutors place of residence (one-to-one or small groups), the tutee's place of residence (usually one-to-one) or special teaching centres (large groups) known as "coaching centres." (Hamid; Sussex & Khan, 2009, p. 281) There are many differences found in the ages and qualifications of private tutors. In many settings, secondary school students earn pocket money by tutoring primary school children, and similarly,

university students tutors secondary students. At other end of the age scale, many tutors are retirees who wish still to contribute to society and earn some extra money. Between these two extremes of age are others who provide tutoring on a full-time or part-time basis, and who may or may not have formal training.

This picture contrasts with mainstream schooling, in which teachers are expected to be aged between 21 and 65 and to have formal training. (Bray, 2006, p.529) Private tutoring is described as a shadow for several reasons. First, it only exists because the mainstream education system exists. Second, it imitates the mainstream: as the mainstream changes in size and orientation, so does the shadow. Third, in almost all societies much more public attention focuses on the mainstream than on its shadow; and fourth, the features of the shadow system are much less distinct than those of the mainstream. Tutoring is a huge industry in much of Asia and is growing fast elsewhere, particularly in Africa, Europe and North America. (Bray, 2005, pp.1-2)

Foondun (2002) has used the term *Private Tuition* and defined it as extra coaching in academic and examinable subjects that is given to students outside school hours for remuneration. On the other hand, Wolf (2002) who was writing about the Third International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) used the term *Extra School Instruction* (ESI) to denote teaching and coaching activities in mathematics and science taking place outside of the regular school structure. It excludes extra help given to students by teachers under the auspices of the school. Following from these descriptions of private tutoring, private schools can be excluded from the category of PST, although private schools constitute an aspect of private education.

Reasons of Private Tutoring

Private tutoring in English is on the increase in urban and rural schools in Bangladesh. It is implemented at all stages of education. Private tutoring in Bangladesh is tutored by mainstream teachers, teachers from other institutions, or students of schools, colleges and universities. According to Hamid et al (2009): The system of private tutoring varies from each other. Students of SSC level are being taught in a small group within 10 to 15 students or in large groups within 20-25 students or more. The placement of the teaching can be the tutor's house, tutee's house, or special teaching places, like coaching centers. Most parents provide their children with private tutors, because they think that it would help them learn the language, or to get higher grades in English subjects; and English is very necessary for future expectations and career opportunities. So many children leave schools with or without break for private tutoring in English. Many others children also receive tutoring on non-school days at weekends, during vacations and on public holidays. (p. 284)

Lack of teachers and a large number of students help to make a large market for tutoring in the country. The rate of private tutoring in the SSC level is on the increase per year over the past decade. Though private tutoring receives popularity among urban students, and many houses, but it is seen to get tutoring even in the lower family.

To get Higher Grades

Teachers cannot teach students English in classroom due to poor time management system. They are not able to teach them English in a proper time. It is hard for the younger learners to realize English Grammar in a very short time. Yet they are determined to cut a good figure in the English exam. They have to rely upon the tutors for learning English and also getting satisfactory results in English.

To decrease the Workload of the Schoolteachers

Private tutoring decreases the workload of school teachers through helping students understand the sources which are supplied in the classrooms. All lessons are not possible to teach in the class, so, in this regard, private tutoring plays an alternative role to develop the students' potential in English.

Lack of Ample Teachers

In Bangladesh, in the SSC level, students are on the increase by leaps and bounds, but teachers are not on the increase in comparison with the students. So, it is not feasible for the teachers to provide quality education in teaching English for all students. As a result, students have to depend on the private tutors due to the lack of ample teachers.

Economic Complexities

Another reason of private tutoring is poor salary of the teachers in Bangladesh. They want to overcome economic crisis, so they are compelled to offer private after school. To earn extra income source, schoolteachers are devoted to private tutoring. Moreover, the economic situation of the teachers are not well-to-do, they have no alternative means without depending upon private tutoring. It may be expressed that private tutoring is their second income source policy to lead their family in Bangladesh.

Lack of Scientific Teaching Capability

Our English teachers are not trained up scientifically in teaching English subjects in the SSC level. Main causes of tutoring education strategy are- poor teaching and learning capability among the teachers and students. If the teachers could be able to provide postmodern education policy in teaching their students English subjects in the classrooms, the students certainly receive scientific education system from the highly qualified English teachers, but here in Bangladesh, the situation is totally opposite.

Necessity of English Learning

There is an important cause of tutoring which is over growing competition in the higher level of education and job market in Bangladesh. Educated and well-to-do guardians expect from their children a very satisfactory result in the English test in order that they can be able to get admitted at Public Institutions, like University, Medical Science, Engineering, Marine Engineering, Humanities, and Business Faculty in the tertiary level with a view to holding the topmost situation in the prevalent job market.

Social Pressure

In Bangladesh, most students receive private tuition in English. Sometimes, social pressure dwindle the students and their parents to get involved in private tutoring. Many younger students are completed to teach SSC level students due to family crisis or limited income source in society and family. Social pressure is a very general matter in our Bangladeshi society. It is certainly a major cause to get oneself engaged in private tutoring.

Parental High Expectations

Many parents have a high expectation for their children. They think that if children are good at English, in course of time, they can be able to get a lucrative job, like teacher, banker, and BCS cadre; and they will be able to have economically developed. So they directly motivate their children to get engaged in private tutoring in English learning so that they can cut a good figure in English subject and in future, their knowledge of English can be able to bring about a significant change in own society and family.

To Improve English Knowledge

Private tutoring is a common platform for learning English. Students want private tutors, because those tutors help them participate effectively in the classroom activities and therefore, the students in the SSC level depend on private tutoring with a view to upgrading their general knowledge of English. Parents have a notion that if their children learn from the tutors, they would learn English language properly and get a satisfactory mark in the examination.

Familial Reasons

There are various reasons why people want to be tutored or to teach as tutors. Private supplementary tutoring improves the students' learning and it also provides constructive activities for children during out-of-school hours. (Bray, 2003, p. 14) Often people who can afford to decide to hire a tutor to teach them or their family members English, because this way of learning English is favorable for all. Parents choose to employ professionally trained tutors, because they are concerned about their children's capability of learning English at school. When being tutored, learners can choose quantity of education provided -- they have to decide on how they take a lesson according to their needs and financial situations. Also, the most significant opportunity of private tutoring is that students can be taught at home, they do not have to attend any classes beyond house or flat, and they can choose when and for how long they want to be tutored according to what suits them the best, which is convenient, especially for students and people working in various times of the day.

Tutors' Reasons

Private tutoring may bring about a potential change in the mental satisfaction of tutors in some families. Some tutors are mainstream teachers who gain extra incomes from supplementary teaching policy, like private tutoring. Others are employees of companies that provide tutoring, or students, retirees or other individuals who are self-employed (Bray, 2005, p. 2). Tutoring can provide a reasonable living for an ESL teacher or an EFL teacher (one who teaches English as a foreign language) in the SSC/HSC/Tertiary level. It has certain merits, one of which is that the tutors can choose their students, so they can teach the learners they like to work with and then, keep teaching them for many years. Tutoring can also be a well-paid part-time job, which is convenient for the tutors who are students themselves. They can decide on the quantity of tutoring – they can offer individual or group lessons. They can choose to teach their classmates or the foreign students who have language difficulties. (Camenson, 2001, p. 12)

Social Insecurity & Eve-teaching

Many parents don't want send the female children outside home due to social insecurity. Social insecurity is a very common problem for the female students in the city or even in the urban areas. For instance, eve-teaching is on the increase day by day across the country, while any female student leaves home for private tutoring or schooling, their parents are very anxious for their children. Due to the fear of eve-teaching, sensitive parents employ tutors at home. In the wealthy family, parents don't like send their female students outside of home for private tutoring.

Negative Aspects of Private tutoring

Private tutoring has also negative aspects in learning English. There have contradictory attitudes to tutoring. At schools, the number of absentees rose high due to private tutoring. Tutoring is reported to have a negative effect on mainstream classes. Yasmeeen (1999) expressed her view regarding the practices of private tutoring:

Most students tend to rely on private tutors for everything including homework and exam tips. As a result classroom attention tends to dwindle creating discipline problems for schoolteachers. Supplementary or top-up teaching is becoming more important than the synergistic classroom experience. (Bray, 2003, p.30)

Students do not pay adequate attention to their lessons, because they have already covered the topics with the help of tutors, and also they aren't satisfied by the teaching process of their schoolteachers. Students think that the instruction in the class is much better rather school teaching in the SSC level. They express their comments as follows:

This has a negative impact upon due respect they have self-confidence in the classroom's teacher and his teaching policy. Negative students' behavior and non-participation in the teaching-learning process turn them into poor quality teaching, for which they have to adhere to private tutoring, and private tuition also leads to negative students' behavior in the class, which turns to deterioration of classroom teaching. (My Translation)

Private tutoring policy develops in family and society, but it also increase disparity between students and teachers. Many parents who have much property as well as financial support can provide more books, learning instruments, and even full-time tutors for the development of their children. But, on the contrary, low income or poor parents cannot provide financial supports for their children, and cannot be able to pay

for private tuition fee in time. Thus, private tutoring increases financial crisis among the poor income families in Bangladesh.

When students of SSC level are away from home and their parents, sometimes, family bonds gets weakened. This is one of the negative aspects of private tutoring. They set out for tutoring classes without having food and they come back home late and feel tired. Private tutoring weakens their health and mentality.

This system puts much loads on the learners who leave home for attending both regular class at school and private tutoring class. It affects the daily life of students for which they are fully deprived of extracurricular activities, recreational activities. Moreover, the negative aspects of private tutoring; there are some major psychological problems between female students and tutors, which are very much common practical issues published in the Daily News and telecast in the social media all the year round. These common problems may be mentioned as follows:

Physical Relation

Due to regular private tutoring at tutor's home and private room, a physical relation is seen between teachers and female students. This current situation is greatly noticed across the country. Female students of SSC level are, of course, immature and innocent mind. They have no practical knowledge of life, and even familial concerns of their own. Emotionally, both teachers and students get themselves engaged into physical relation with each other. They fail to control emotion, feeling and fancy. Tutors in Bangladesh are like vagabonds, most of them have no permanent residence or dwelling place, they just tutor female students for the temporary basis to his own bear education expenses, to maintain familial crisis, and to lead a fops and foolish life style in the urban and city areas in today's Bangladesh. Anyway, this type of physical relation becomes a severe problem for the immature ones.

Marriage Relation

Many a times, in Bangladeshi society and family, private tutoring may be regarded as a negative issue of early marriage. Both students and teachers get themselves married very early in their immature life without parental consents and permission. Early marriage brings about a tragic downfall in the minds of both teachers and students. As we know that Bangladesh sometimes fails to afford her large population economically and socially. At such critical and juncture situation, if early marriage is on the increase due to private tutoring, the nation will have to face a hurdled situation.

Familial Trauma

Separation, divorce, and familial crisis are now-a-days observed due to private tutoring. Many married tutors are addicted to illicit relationship with their female students. Sometimes they get married their students, keeping the whole matter secret to their students and even to their own family. Immature students unknowingly fall victim of familial crisis. As a result, the future dream and expectation of female students remain unfulfilled and unveiled. At one time they have to bear a big burden on their shoulders throughout their life, and their long awaited dream gets mixed with dust and sand.

Question Paper Leak

Now-a-days it is seen that most of the question papers are leaked due to private tutoring across the country. Some greedy and dishonest academicians, tutors, and even high official of Education Board leak the question papers just before the examination commences throughout the country. And, they sell the questions to students and ignorant parents at a cheaper rate and sometimes high rate. The government fails to tackle the situation due to the political crisis in the country.

Methodology & Data Collection

In the research project, information about the practices and policies of tutoring had been collected from different types of participants, including--schoolteachers, tutors, students of SSC level and their parents. In this field survey, 10 schoolteachers, 25 students, 5 tutors, and 15 parents did take an active part at Tongi under the district of Gazipur. The sample for the teachers, students and parents was a convenience one as some of them were unwilling to express their personal views regarding private tuition fee/monthly payment basis face to face while the interview was being taken. The participants were asked to tick the right option out of four. Different categories of easy and simple questions were provided so that the participants could answer the questions easily. Four types of question set were prepared for the students, schoolteachers, tutors and learned parents (selected). Through the question pattern for the schoolteachers and tutors, reasons for giving private tuition, the common organization of a typical tuition session, how the tuition sessions were connected to the task done among the SSC level students near by a coaching centre at Tongi, their assigned teachers and other important information about private tutoring and its tuition system were investigated. Further clarifications were done through an interview with other students and guidance.

The sample of students were asked to answer the multiple choice relating to the reasons for taking private tuition in English Language Learning, how private tutoring helps the students of the SSC level understand English Grammatical skill, reading comprehension, composition, application, paragraph, letter, story writing and vocabulary. The researcher had to spend 10 days to collect data so that he could enable to show a faithful picture of private tutoring in the SSC level of 21st -century Bangladeshi EFL learners.

The researcher proposed the topics for discussion during the interview process, but asked few specific questions. (Rubin & Rubin, 1995) During each of the interviews, the researcher recorded the interview and prompted the participants to express what they thought were the reasons of their resorting to private tutoring in learning English, and what effects private tutoring had on students' learning capability.

Because the format of the different types of interviewing process was open, some participants responded with more details, while others simply agreed with what had been said. Students' and parents' interviews lasted for approximately several hours, respectively. After the interviews were completed, the researcher went through the audio recording, and transcribed the two interviews by noting complete thoughts and useful information.

Data Analysis

The content of the participants' responses in different types of interviews was investigated and coded. According to Rubin and Rubin (1995), "Coding is the process of grouping interviewees' responses into categories that bring together the similar ideas, concepts, or themes you have discovered". (p. 238) In coding the interview data, the researcher checked the question paper very carefully what type of option they tick-marked out of four that caught his much attention to serve as a category. This procedure enabled the researcher to gather new information into categories or central themes, including To get Higher Grades, to decrease the Workload of the Schoolteachers, lack of ample teachers, economic constraints, lack of scientific teaching capability, necessity of English learning, social pressure, parental high expectations, to improve English knowledge, familial reasons, tutors' reasons, social insecurity & eve-teaching, and so on. Active participants like schoolteachers, tutors, students and their parents groups did express different views about the causes and impacts of Private Tutoring on English Language Learning. Responses from the participants were compiled and problems and reasons for private tutoring emerged from the data.

In the graph it is seen that there were 10 teachers, 25 students, 5 tutors, and 15 parents who actively participated in the field survey.

They expressed different views regarding current Private Tutoring System of Bangladesh. From their viewpoints, it became very easy for the researcher to investigate the reasons, negative aspects, findings, and recommendations of Private Tutoring so that he would unveil an implementers dimension for the Secondary Level learners of Bangladesh Education System.

No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	a=	b=	c=	d=
1	a	a	b	a	c	c	b	c	a	a	5	2	3	0
2	a	a	c	b	a	b	b	d	a	b	4	4	1	1
3	b	d	c	d	c	d	d	a	b	a	2	2	2	4
4	b	a	a	b	b	a	b	d	c	b	3	5	1	1
5	a	c	b	d	b	b	d	c	c	a	2	3	3	2
6	d	c	a	a	d	a	a	a	b	d	5	1	1	3
7	b	d	c	b	a	b	d	c	b	a	2	4	2	2
8	a	a	b	a	c	a	d	a	a	b	6	2	1	1
9	a	b	a	d	a	b	b	a	c	a	5	3	1	1
10	a	b	b	a	c	d	a	c	c	d	3	2	3	2
11	b	b	c	b	c	b	c	a	d	b	1	5	3	1
12	c	b	c	a	d	a	d	c	b	a	3	2	3	2
13	a	b	b	a	c	a	b	a	a	a	6	3	1	0
14	c	d	c	d	b	d	a	c	c	d	1	1	4	4
15	a	d	c	b	a	b	b	c	c	a	3	3	3	1
16	b	d	c	d	b	c	a	b	c	c	1	3	4	2
17	a	a	b	d	b	c	a	a	b	d	4	3	1	2

18	b	a	c	d	b	a	b	a	c	a	4	3	2	1
19	a	c	d	b	c	a	b	d	a	b	3	3	2	2
20	a	a	c	b	d	b	a	c	a	a	5	2	2	1
21	a	b	a	a	c	a	b	a	a	a	7	2	1	0
22	a	b	c	d	a	b	c	b	a	b	3	4	2	1
23	a	b	b	a	a	a	b	a	a	b	6	4	0	0
24	a	b	c	a	b	d	a	b	c	a	4	3	2	1
25	a	b	c	d	a	c	a	b	c	a	4	2	3	1
	Total										90	71	51	36

Students' Questionnaire Survey

From this chart it is seen that there were 25 students, including male and female who participated in the survey. Question set was provided to the students in the coaching centre where they were being taught. There were four options in the question pattern. 25 sets of question were given to each of the students in the tutorial home. It took 20 minutes to answer the question. Then the questions were taken from them. While the researcher scrutinized their questions very carefully, it was found that most of the students gave the tick mark on 'a' option whose total summation was 90. Then they chose 'b' option which was 71, and 'c' was the third choice and 'd' was the least choice option. The survey showed that 'a' option was the topmost choice of the students and 'd' option was their last choice which was only 36.

In this pie chart it is seen that there were 248 options in the questions' pattern and 25 students took an active part in the survey. There were different types of multiple choices regarding private tutoring. They were asked to tick the right answer out of four. Maximum students chose 'a' option whose rate was-36.29%. Their second choice

was 'b' option consisting of 28.62% and the last choice was 'd' where the rate of their choice was 14.51%.

No	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	a=	b=	c=	d=
1	a	b	a	a	b	a	d	c	a	a	6	2	1	1
2	d	a	b	c	a	a	d	b	a	c	4	2	2	2
3	c	a	c	a	c	a	a	c	d	b	4	1	4	1
4	d	a	c	c	a	d	c	b	b	c	2	2	4	2
5	b	a	c	b	c	a	d	c	c	a	3	2	4	1
6	d	a	a	c	b	a	a	c	b	a	5	2	2	1
7	d	a	c	d	c	a	d	c	a	b	3	1	3	3
8	b	a	c	c	a	c	c	b	b	b	2	4	4	0
9	c	a	c	b	c	a	c	c	d	a	3	1	5	1
10	a	a	c	c	b	a	d	c	d	a	4	1	3	2
Total											36	18	32	14

Teachers' Questionnaire Survey

From this chart it is seen that there were 10 teachers who actively participated in the survey. 10 sets of question were given to each of the teacher about private tutoring. It took 10 minutes to answer the question. Then the questions were taken from them. While the researcher checked their questions, it was found that most of the teachers ticked 'a' option whose total summation was 36. Then they chose 'b' option which was 18, and 'c' was their final choice which was only 14. After the survey, they expressed different opinions regard private tutoring with the current researcher.

In this pie chart it is seen that 10 teachers took an active part in the survey. There were different types of multiple choices regarding private tutoring. Teachers were asked to tick the right answer out of four options. They chose 'a' option whose rate was-36%. Their second choice was 'c' option consisting of 32% and their last choice was 'd' where the rate was 14%.

No	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	a=	b=	c=	d=
1	b	a	a	a	b	a	a	d	a	b	6	3	0	1
2	a	b	b	b	a	b	d	a	a	a	5	4	0	1
3	c	d	a	b	a	a	a	a	d	b	5	2	1	2
4	b	c	d	b	d	c	a	d	b	a	2	3	2	3
5	b	a	a	a	b	a	a	d	a	b	6	3	0	1
Total											24	15	3	8

Tutors' Survey Questionnaire

From this chart we see that there were 5 tutors who joined during the survey. 5 sets of question were given to each of the tutor. It took 10 minutes to answer the question. Then the questions were taken from them. While the researcher checked the question carefully, it was found that they ticked 'a' out of four options where the total summation stood 24. Then they chose 'b' option which was 15, and 'c' was their last choice which was only 3. After the survey was completed, tutors opined differently concerning private tutoring with the researcher.

In this pie chart it is found that there were 50 options in the questions' pattern. For this only 5 tutors took an active part in the survey. There were different categories of multiple choices regarding private tutoring. Tutors were asked to tick the right option out of four. They ticked 'a' option in which the rate was-48%. Their second choice was 'b' option consisting of 30%. Their third choice was 'c' option which was the least and

it was only 6%. After the survey was done, they expressed their practical experiences with the researcher.

No	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	a=	b=	c=	d=
1	a	b	a	d	a	a	a	a	c	b	6	2	1	1
2	b	c	d	d	b	a	c	a	c	a	3	2	3	2
3	a	b	d	d	b	a	c	c	c	d	2	2	3	3
4	a	a	d	d	b	d	a	c	b	a	4	2	1	3
5	a	a	d	d	c	d	c	b	c	b	2	2	3	3
6	a	b	b	a	b	b	a	c	c	a	4	4	2	0
7	c	c	d	d	b	a	a	c	b	d	2	2	3	3
8	a	c	b	d	b	a	c	a	c	b	3	3	3	1
9	a	d	d	c	a	c	b	b	c	b	2	3	3	2
10	a	a	d	c	a	b	c	c	a	d	4	1	3	2
11	a	c	d	d	b	a	c	b	c	b	2	3	3	2
12	a	c	d	a	b	b	c	a	c	b	3	3	3	1
13	a	c	d	a	c	a	c	b	c	a	4	1	4	1
14	a	b	d	d	c	a	c	b	c	a	3	2	3	2
15	c	a	d	a	d	a	c	b	a	b	4	2	2	2
Total											48	34	40	26

Parents' Survey Questionnaire

From this chart it is seen that there were 15 guardians who participated in this investigation. 15 sets of question were handed over to each of the guardian. It took 20 minutes to answer the question. Then the questions were taken from them. When the researcher evaluated their questions, it was seen that the parents of the students ticked 'a' option whose total summation was 48. Then they chose 'b' option which was 34, and 'c' was their second choice which was 40. Their last choice was 'd' which was only 26. After the survey, the guardians expressed their individual opinions very closely with the researcher.

In this pie chart it is found that there were 148 options in the questions' pattern. For this purpose, 15 educated guardians were selected for completing the survey. There were different categories of multiple choices based upon private tutoring. Parents were asked to tick the right option out of four. They ticked 'a' option in which the rate stood-32.43%. Their second choice was 'c' option consisting of 27.02%. Their last choice was 'd' option which was the least and it was only 17.57%. After the survey was done, they expressed various opinions with the researcher freely.

Findings

This research project shows that most of the students of SSC level have to depend upon the private tutors throughout the country rather than their school teachers due to time constraints in the classroom and the failure of the teachers. Students have to face different types of social problems for private tutoring in Bangladesh, especially for girls, like eve-teasing, kidnapping, psychological problems and recent occurrence, like question paper leak. Due to economic constraints, both teachers and tutors get themselves involved in private tutoring with a view to maintaining familial issues. This study also shows that both teachers and tutors regard private tutoring as a weapon of income source in a developing country, like Bangladesh. Many poor parents cannot afford to bear educational expenses for private tutoring because they are financially poor and weak. Anyway, many students and their guardians think that it is not possible to cut a good figure in the SSC examination without private tutoring though the present government is trying to ban this system very strictly.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This research project focuses on the reasons and problems of private tutoring in the Secondary Level of Bangladesh Education System. From the above discussion it can be said that private tutoring has not only positive aspects, but also negative aspects. Private tutors help his students solve the complex problems of what they cannot be able to learn from their schoolteachers. The weaker students need learning supports in English subjects which are guided by the tutors. It would not be a right decision for the Bangladesh Government to ban the private tutoring centers. Learners should understand why they need private tutors and how they can be benefitted from their tutors. Bangladesh Government should raise awareness about the practical merits of private tutoring for the student of SSC level. Private tutoring has both positive and negative aspects. Guardians and learners ought not to rely on private tutors. We would try to find out better effects of private tutoring and make the best use of it. So some important suggestions are given below:

- At first, the education system of Bangladeshi institutions must be modified and updated. Many students in a class fall victim of such problems. As there are many learners, teachers cannot be able to attract the attention of all students.
- Another problem is that while teaching, English is not given priority may be weakness in basic skill of English. In the class, all subjects are taught in a proper way, and English should be taught like other subjects. But, the researcher thinks, English, including grammar, reading comprehension, vocabulary, speaking, and writing skill need to be given special care.
- After studying English for so many years, students cannot be able to communicate in English satisfactorily. So, it needs to be practiced more and more. In this case, students can take help from their private tutors make English language learning very effectively.
- Weaker students can be sent to private tutors for a scheduled time. Private tutors should try to find out their problematic issue show it can be solved as earliest possible.
- The effective teaching of English Grammar in the secondary level may be ensured by the right kind of attitude towards teaching and learning English.
- It has to be ensured that teachers implement their knowledge achieving through the proper training course.
- New teaching methods have to be implemented.
- A suitable classroom environment is to be created.
- Classes should be interesting so that the students can get motivated to learn English Grammar very easily.
- Awareness should be raised in teaching and learning English Grammar with vocabulary and speaking.
- Expert English teachers must be recruited and free and fair recruitment policy must be ensured.
- Stipend must be provided for the poor and meritorious students.
- Ultra-modern amenities must be ensured for the Secondary Level Learners.
- Lastly, recommended for school teachers, private tutors, students and even their parents should be conscious of all subjects, especially Mathematics, English, Accounting, and Science. The Government should provide scientific training approach for the teachers. English learning centre ought to be established at schools; expert teachers should be appointed to develop the potential of the students and he should very strictly ban the leaked question paper at any cost.
- Criminals should be punished with an iron rod so that nobody can dare to do such a heinous act in future.

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